

AMPERE: A new Project for Innovative Heterojunction Manufacturing Solutions to Improve Competitiveness of the European PV Manufacturing Industry.

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Abstract

The European PV manufacturing industry has faced strong foreign competition in the last years, which has led to a dramatic reduction of its production capacity. It has completely shifted from a massive leadership at the beginning of the new millennium, with five EU companies in the top ten manufacturers, to a situation of survival where few of them are struggling in an actual extremely competitive market. Europe still has solid industrial assets consisting of silicon & material suppliers, and high quality equipment suppliers that constitute the core of a value chain to be rebuilt.

AMPERE, acronym for Automated photovoltaic cell and Module industrial Production to regain and secure European Renewable Energy market, was born for these purposes. AMPERE project aims to the setting-up of an innovative 100 MWp/y full-scale automated pilot line at the 3SUN module PV production line delivering a power module of 380 Wp (bifacial G/G 72-cells). Soon after the end of the project a rapid scale up to 240 MWp/y is planned and a route paving the way to the GWp/y scale will deliver the roadmap to reach production capacity stated. The project will operate with the support of the technological platforms for solar cells at CEA-INES and modules at MBR, the platform for advanced module technologies at MBS along with the support of high level research institutes (CSEM, EPFL, F-ISE, ENEA, CNR) as well as key EU companies covering the whole PV value chain (Norsun, Rise technology, Jonas & Redmann, ERM). Ampere has EGP as internal end-user and with the support of the project it will target an LCOE reduction of at least 15% compared to conventional PV mc-Si technology.

Keywords: production-line, heterojunction.

1 INTRODUCTION

A race towards lower costs and higher competitiveness in PV sector has led to a readily decrease of module prices over time as the historical PV Learning Curve teaches; Asian manufacturers seem to have regained margins and their overcapacities still represent a risk for price decrease and price stabilization cannot reasonably be expected in the coming years [1]. The EU value chain has not entirely disappeared yet, as European equipment suppliers have temporarily benefited from the strong Asian demand. But on long term basis, due to its large domination in PV manufacturing, Asia will attract and create a large part of the forthcoming PV material and equipment suppliers, thus reducing even more the PV European system. European research institutes and equipment manufacturers are still global technology leaders. But the loss of their domestic European customer base seriously jeopardizes this position and their financing. If Europe wants to play a role in the future of photovoltaics, one of the main pillars of future energy

supply, it needs to maintain a vital ecosystem along the whole value chain including R&D labs, equipment manufacturers and manufacturing companies. The Ampere project aims to assure the full value chain sustainability in Europe. The sustainability assessment will consider how extended life and improved efficiency will improve known upstream and downstream issues and the results can inform future PV design aspects and criteria. Since the global market for very high efficiency cells is still small but rapidly expanding, upgrading and expanding capacities for high efficiency technology and building up new capacities in Europe with a technology based on high innovation such as Heterojunction, might be achieved rapidly without jeopardizing the efforts of existing European manufacturers to compete on global markets with incremental improvements of mature technologies.

AMPERE will try to follow this goal, aiming at establishing a next generation PV technology with cell efficiencies of 22.5% at production level in the 100MWp/y (and to improve efficiency on the subsequent

development of 250 MWp/y lines after the project, to achieve an average efficiency of 23.5% and more), very high quality, high innovation rates, large scale manufacturing and a certain extent of vertical integration for reaching and maintaining a globally competitive position. Moreover, industrial deployment of PV manufacturing and market presence requires considerable size and capital to be competitive at a global level: Having large players in Europe mastering subsequent technology generations is a precondition for maintaining this ecosystem, investing in new technology generations, re-creating employment in the PV sector, re-conquering a strong position on global markets and ensuring a lasting European capacity in this key technology for the transition to sustainable energy supply systems. For the purpose it will focus on the industrialization and automation of innovative HJT technologies, based on a well-developed, assessed and demonstrated HJT owing to the main partners of the consortium [2], [3], [4]. The project involves a strong industrial and academic partners with a wide value chain represented by European leading industries, from technology providers/developers (NORSUN and MEYER BURGER) to manufacturer (3SUN) and finally to end-user (EGP). The main objective of AMPERE is to develop and secure the European supply chain of PV manufacturing by implementing a large scale cell and module industrial pilot lines. The implementation of innovative technologies into these industrial manufacturing lines will demonstrate that a larger production of PV products at a competitive COO and subsequent LCOE compared to non-European manufacturer is possible.

AMPERE main technology is focused on the demonstration of feasibility of bi-facial cells and modules based on heterojunction technology (HJT) at a 100 MWp/y industrial pilot line. Soon after the project it should lead to a short-scale upgrade at 250 MWp/y and then show the path to the GWp/y-scale; the project will deliver the roadmap to reach the production capacity stated. The project will be focused on the improved PV module power, reliability and durability to reduce the cost needed to fix and maintain PV plant and decrease its operational risks. The metric will be applied on the existing PV module industrial production site of 3SUN in Catania, Italy[4] (Fig.1).

Figure1: 3SUN PV module industrial production site, Catania, Italy.

2 APPROACH

During the recent past, it has been proven that silicon heterojunction solar cells can achieve efficiencies more than 26 % as Kaneka, with the support of IMEC, has

showed recently [5]. However, most of these record cells have been achieved at the R&D scale and only few companies are producing Si-HJT cells and modules on a mass production level. Though SHJ technology has long shown great potential in achieving high cell & module efficiency, its production capacity has been low and further expansion is slow, mainly due to difficulties in developing high efficiency solar cell technology, as well as high capital cost to build SHJ production line [6].

Amperre basic approach starts through modification and upgrading of the pre-existing 3-SUN thin film silicon PV. So far, 3SUN has produced more than 6 million of thin film silicon PV modules, with annual capacity of 200MWp/y. The new investment plan has the scope of renewing the technology and reusing at least part of the existing expensive equipment (such as the PECVD Cluster tools for a-Si deposition) and facilities, which today are used for thin film PV manufacturing. HJT can leverage on higher annual energy generation owing to bifacial characteristics and to a low thermal coefficient.

Figure 2: Ampere technology expected positioning in terms of LCOE compared with premium PV market.

Moreover, the glass-glass technology, which 3SUN has utilized for several years in its manufacturing process, will be fundamental for improving the reliability and hence the lifetime of the 3SUN modules installed in EGP power plants, allowing the energy company to realize plants with minimized energy generation costs (LCOE). Key advantages of this approach includes the cell efficiency improvement from 10% to >22% and lower capital cost. The major items inherent to the line conversion are: the modification of equipment PECVD, transfer and material handling systems, integration of thin-film and c-Si production equipment.

AMPERE will start from existing technologies that have been demonstrated their effectiveness during previous European successful projects. Cells Technological Platform of CEA-INES (TRL6) [2] and Module Technological Platform of MBR (TRL6)[3] will be the first two bricks of the project where a technology selection process will enable the implementation of the best materials and instruments into the existing industrial production line of 3SUN (TRL 7-8) [4], which will work as demonstration bed. By establishing a cell and module industrial production line of 100 MWp/y representative of the large scale production, AMPERE will trigger new activities in the European PV value chain to revitalize the sector. It is expected that with HJT bifacial modules (380 Wp bifacial G/G 72-cells) the LCOE will be reduced of at least 15% compared to the main technologies on the market in most of the geographical areas of interest [5]. The recent trend shows a continuous decrease of module prices which have reached <0,5 €/Wp for premium

will lead to reduce LCOE of at least 10%.

Figure 6. Ampere yearly targets and its implementation.

For this reason, in the segment of the utility power plants market, a scale of 250MWp/y can be enough to allow EGP to compete with the conventional technologies (mostly mc-Si and CdTe) as reported in Table II.

Table II: Cost of goods (COGS) of 3SUN expected 250 MWp industrial line

250MWp Manufacturing Line	2020	2022	2024
HJT Costs (€/Wp)	0,42	0,38	0,34
Estimated reduction in LCOE with respect to mc-Si (in the same geographical area)	10%	12%	15%

From 3SUN viewpoint the factory will operate with a positive margin of about 9% in order to allow an adequate return on investment for 3SUN and to maximize the benefits in terms of LCOE for the mother company (EGP). The technology roadmap for EGP/3SUN with the main expected improvements related to new technology bricks implementation developed in the AMPERE projects is reported in Table 3 for the period 2020 – 2024.

Table III. Timeline of expected improvements for the implementation of new technology bricks

Year	2020	2022	2024
Cell Eff (%)	22,5	23,5	24
Module Power (Wp)	380	390	400

Ampere project will deliver the roadmap to reach 1 GW production capacity. Increasing to 1GWp scale will reduce the costs. 3SUN has estimated a budgetary cost under 0.3€/Wp for a gigawatt scale manufacturing in the 3SUN factory, in which they could partially leverage on the already existing facilities.

The benefits arising from the economy of scale are reported in Table IV, and they will position the HJT technology in a leading position not only for the utility scale market but also for the roof top sector where the technology will be surely considered as premium one and will compete with the high performance technologies allowing even larger margins due to the lower manufacturing costs.

Table IV. Cost of goods (COGS) of 3SUN expected 1 GWp industrial line

1GWp/y Manufacturing Line	2022	2024
HJT Costs (€/Wp)	0.28	0.25
Estimated reduction in LCOE with respect to mc-Si (in the same geographical area)	15%	20%

5. CONCLUSION.

A premium technology with high efficiency, high reliability, low temperature coefficient and consequently low LCOE will be industrialized in Europe, through the Ampere project. Premium segment is a very attractive option for utility scale PV market segments as it translates directly into very low LCOE. For such market segments, bifacial solar cells increase the annual generation of energy. The advantages in terms of energy gain can be even improved by using HJT technology, due to lower thermal budget and expected lower degradation rate[8]. The aim of the AMPERE project is to demonstrate EU innovative and sustainable manufacturing of bifacial modules in a pilot line capable of manufacturing up to 100MW/y of modules. These expected outcomes will be assessed and evaluated as a solid milestone for the viability of a 250 MWp/y production scale factory in 2020.

The manufactured products are based on silicon hetero-junction technology PV cells with mean efficiency of 22.5%. These will be industrialised applying innovative production processes that require fewer steps than conventional crystalline-silicon PV cell technologies. The route to implement to 250 MWp/y the production line has been settled together with the efficiency targeted at 23.5% after the end of project. The project will deliver the roadmap to reach the GW/y-scale production capacity with a corresponding LCOE reduction of 15% respect to the mainstream mc-Si technology and will provide investment pathways for the exploitation of the results to support the GW facilities of the next 5-10 years.

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